

1 TNF superfamily genes likely exert critical functions during lineage commitment in the human embryo.

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3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here a group of tumor
9 necrosis factor TNF superfamily genes with functions in lineage commitment in embryonic stem cells of
10 the human embryo.

11 Citations

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